

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION ON THE EFFICACY AND LONG-TERM CONTENTMENT OF INTENSE REHABILITATION THERAPY POST BRAIN TUMOR SURGERY

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INTRODUCTION

Brain tumors represent a significant cause of disability, with a rising prevalence of intracranial tumors. Advances in surgical, chemotherapeutic, and radiotherapeutic techniques have notably improved the survival rates of brain tumor patients. Consequently, there is a growing imperative to address residual neurological impairments and enhance the quality of life for survivors. Rehabilitation therapy post-brain tumor surgery has garnered increasing attention as a means to achieve these goals. Despite this, rehabilitation following brain tumor surgery has often been overlooked by neurosurgeons, neuro-oncologists, and physiatrists, who may perceive limited survival rates and high recurrence rates among these patients.

The necessity for rehabilitation in cancer patients was highlighted by Lehmann et al. in 1978, sparking subsequent research into its impact on functional outcomes and neurological recovery in brain tumor patients. Notably, the similarity in symptoms between stroke and brain tumor patients (such as cognitive impairment, motor dysfunction, sensory deficits, ataxia, dysphagia, aphasia, and visual perception deficits) has led to comparable findings regarding the effectiveness of rehabilitation therapy in both groups.

While short-term benefits of rehabilitation therapy in brain tumor patients are acknowledged, debates persist over its meaningfulness and necessity in light of low survival and high recurrence rates. To date, no studies have directly addressed this critical question. In the absence of a definitive indicator of the potential need and benefit of rehabilitation for brain tumor patients, the long-term satisfaction of family caregivers may serve as a surrogate measure, reflecting the evolution of neurological function throughout the patients' remaining lifespan.

This study aims to comparatively evaluate the effectiveness of intensive rehabilitation therapy in improving neurological deficits following brain tumor surgery, using functional outcomes in stroke patients as a reference point, given the established efficacy of intensive rehabilitation in this population; and assess the perspectives of family caregivers regarding their long-term satisfaction with intensive rehabilitation, considering patients' survival and functional status.

Keywords: Brain neoplasms, Treatment outcome, Satisfaction, Neurological rehabilitation

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study received approval from the Scientific and practical center of neurosurgery of the Republic of Uzbekistan. We conducted a retrospective review of medical records from a rehabilitation center affiliated with a single university hospital, identifying patients with neurological impairments following brain tumor resection surgery or stroke who underwent intensive rehabilitation between December 2019 and May 2023.

To mitigate bias, all eligible patients meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria during the study period were included. Inclusion criteria comprised presence of brain tumor or stroke confirmed by computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging; admission for rehabilitation within <4 months of brain tumor resection surgery or stroke onset; age >18 years; and discharge for >1 year. Exclusion criteria encompassed concurrent neurodegenerative diseases; and persistent minimally conscious state or vegetative status. Patients with brain tumors were stratified into subgroups based on malignancy status (benign and malignant) as per the World Health Organization classification .

The rehabilitation center adheres to a standardized procedure for initial functional assessment shortly after admission and subsequent follow-up assessment at >1 month post-admission. Standard rehabilitation therapy comprised 1-hour sessions of physical therapy and occupational therapy each, administered 5 days a week during hospitalization. The objective of rehabilitation therapy for patients with neurological deficits was to enhance their self-management capabilities. The rehabilitation protocol was formulated by the clinical therapy team.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Study Participants

Among the 35 brain tumor patients included, 21 had benign tumors, and 14 had malignant tumors. Additionally, 108 stroke patients were enrolled as controls. The average age was 57.6 years for the brain tumor group and 60.9 years for the stroke group. Baseline demographics, including age, sex, lesion side, and duration of inpatient rehabilitation, were comparable between the two groups. Similarly, baseline characteristics did not significantly differ between benign and malignant tumor subgroups. Among brain tumor patients, 24 (68.6%) had primary tumors, while 11 (31.4%) had recurrent tumors.

No notable differences were observed in ECOG score, tumor location, or lesion size between the benign and malignant tumor subgroups. Nonetheless, variations were noted in treatment modality preference and recurrence rate between these subgroups.

Rehabilitation Results

Significant enhancements were observed in FMA, BBS, K-MBI, KMMSE, and IQ scores within both the brain tumor and stroke cohorts (each $p < 0.001$), as well as within the benign and malignant brain tumor subgroups (each $p < 0.05$). No significant disparities were found between groups or subgroups in terms of effectiveness or efficiency. In brain tumor patients, malignancy status did not exert a significant impact on the enhancement of ECOG scores. Nevertheless, the ultimate rehabilitation outcome exhibited a significant correlation with the initial functional status. In simpler terms, brain tumor patients with a more favorable baseline function for a specific parameter demonstrated a greater improvement in that particular parameter. To elaborate, improvements in FMA, BBS, and K-MBI scores were notably associated with their respective baseline values. Additionally, enhancements in K-MMSE and IQ scores were significantly correlated with both the initial KMMSE score and the initial IQ score.

DISCUSSION

In this investigation, we observed significant functional enhancements in brain tumor patients who underwent intensive rehabilitation targeting motor skills, balance, cognition, and activities of daily living (ADL). Remarkably, these improvements were comparable to those

seen in stroke patients and remained consistent regardless of malignancy status. Moreover, our survey of family caregivers, conducted 1 to 4 years post-intensive rehabilitation, indicated that brain tumor survivors maintained relatively robust levels of motor function, cognition, and ADL capability. Notably, caregivers expressed high levels of long-term satisfaction with the intensive rehabilitation therapy, despite the presence of a significant proportion of patients with malignant tumors or those who had deceased.

The demand for intensive rehabilitation therapy is steadily rising with advancements in treatment options. However, it appears underutilized in brain tumor patients, particularly those with malignant tumors. Several factors contribute to this underutilization. Firstly, despite improvements, the 5-year survival rate for malignant brain tumors remains relatively low, hovering around 37.5% as of 2011. Secondly, the recurrence rate for malignant brain tumors, notably glioblastoma, is alarmingly high, nearing 100%. Given these grim statistics, physiatrists may hesitate to prescribe rehabilitation therapy for brain tumor survivors.

Previous studies, including Sherer et al., have explored functional recovery in brain tumor patients undergoing rehabilitation, reporting positive outcomes in a subset of patients. Notably, functional recovery was found to be akin to that observed in stroke patients across various domains, including locomotor function, cognition, and ADLs. Our findings align with these prior observations, demonstrating similar improvements in upper extremity motor function (FMA score), balance (BBS score), ADL function (K-MBI score), and cognition (KMMSE and IQ scores) in both brain tumor and stroke patients. Additionally, we noted significant enhancements in ECOG scores among patients with benign and malignant tumors alike, with no discernible difference between the subgroups. These results underscore the efficacy of rehabilitation in facilitating functional recovery following surgery for both benign and malignant brain tumors.

Past research on stroke patients employing measures like the Barthel Index and the Functional Independence Measure has indicated that poorer functional status upon admission correlates with less substantial functional improvements. Furthermore, the initial degree of impairment serves as a predictor of rehabilitation effectiveness for motor and cognitive function recovery in stroke patients. Our present findings reinforce these observations, revealing significant correlations between initial motor, ADL, and cognitive function scores and their corresponding outcomes in brain tumor patients.

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